

Deliverable D7

Landscape document identifying standardization requirements for microfluidic component design and manufacturing with respect to modularity and heterogenous integration

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1 Scope

This document provides a landscape document identifying areas suitable for standardization and areas less suitable with respect to modularity and heterogeneous integration. The landscape document will focus on key aspects for the design of modular microfluidic components and integration of heterogeneous components into microfluidics under consideration of substrate materials.

A4.2.3 M19	<p>Using input from A4.2.1 and A4.2.2, microfluidic with support from INESC MN, CEA, EnablingMNT, IMTAG, UofG, LNE and BHT will produce landscape document identifying areas suitable for standardisation and areas less suitable with respect to modularity and heterogeneous integration. The landscape document will focus on key aspects for the design of modular microfluidic components and integration of heterogeneous components into microfluidics under consideration of substrate materials (e.g. polymers, glass, Si). The landscape document will be disseminated to standardisation organisations ISO/TC48/WG3 and WG5, ISO/TC69/SC6, ISO/TC229, ISO/TC276, IMEKO TC7, CCM WGFF, CEN/TC332/WG7 and EURAMET TC-Flow.</p> <p>Once agreed by the consortium, the coordinator on behalf of microfluidic, INESC MN, CEA, EnablingMNT, IMTAG, UofG, LNE and BHT will submit the landscape document to EURAMET as D7: <i>'Landscape document identifying standardisation requirements for microfluidic component design and manufacturing with respect to modularity and heterogeneous sensor integration'</i>.</p>	<p>microfluidic, INESC MN, CEA, EnablingMNT, IMTAG, UofG, BHT, LNE</p>
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2 Introduction

When investigating the field of microfluidics, there are several different ways of commercial pathways and applications that define the need for standardization. This results in three areas:

1. **No standards necessary:** E.g. a stand-alone device with a dedicated instrument does not need standardization in itself but it might be relevant to follow existing standards e.g. if some components of an instrument should be used which are of-the-shelf, or if existing fabrication equipment can be used for the fabrication of the device.
2. **Using existing standards:** Taking commodity devices that should be used with existing laboratory equipment, keeping with existing standards from laboratory automation (SBS - Society for Biomolecular Screening / ANSI – American National Standards Institute) is a MUST for their use and a wide acceptance of the devices. Next to this, fabrication always benefits from the use of standards. Against this background the standards that have been successfully applied in microfluidics relate the SBS/ANSI standard for the microtiter plate and the use of the microscopy slide's outer format following standards as well. Looking from a fabrication point of view, standardization matters in a manner that existing equipment can be used: E.g. for reagent integration keeping with pitches of 9 mm, 4.5 mm or 2.25 mm has the benefit that existing pipettors can be used, standard formats also allow in particular for smaller series to make use of family tools for injection moulding and existing fabrication set-ups, cutting fabrication cost.
3. **Defining new standards:** Standards can be useful to create new modular systems. Ideally, in a modular setup, each component can be tested and evaluated separately, components can be replaced easily and even the whole system can be reconfigured. Modularity have long been a holy grail for microfluidics. Many scientists have proposed systems to achieve this, but, like the better mousetrap, they all failed to be adopted outside of the scientific group that defined it.

We realised that there are two important boundary conditions to meet to realise general acceptance of a microfluidic component standard interface:

A key aspect of modular integration is how to make the electrical, optical and/or microfluidic connections. Besides this one should consider dimensional aspects like footprint, sealing and the method to fix the component. But first and foremost, one should consider the requirements for such a modular approach. A big problem here is the plethora of modules and systems on a market, with many different applications and many, sometimes conflicting requirements for modular integration and combination.

Figure 1: Example of a modular approach not making it to a commercially accepted and well-known approach.

Designing such standard systems only makes sense if a sufficient number of component suppliers agree to make components that fit into the system. An important part of an endeavour to come to such a standard will be to discuss this with the supply chain, to ensure availability and provide application examples. Allowing microfluidics a better entry in the routine life science / analytical laboratory, designers and manufacturers of microfluidic components like pumps, sensors etc. need to be part of the overall interfacing concept discussions as well.

Looking from a fabrication point of view, standardization matters in a manner that existing equipment can be used: E.g. for reagent integration keeping with pitches of 9 mm, 4.5 mm or 2.25 mm has the benefit that existing pipettors as shown above can be used, standard formats also allow in particular for smaller series to make use of family tools for injection moulding and existing fabrication set-ups, cutting fabrication cost by a factor of 10.

3 The importance of standardization in modularity and sensor integration

From the design point of view, standardization is important, when devices and systems need to be combined, e.g.:

1. Existing equipment from e.g. laboratory automation, liquid handling, inspection or fabrication aspects.
2. Existing components that must interface from the use-case requirements: e.g. syringes, swabs, pipettes, electronic contacts etc.
3. When it's necessary to use components from external suppliers, in a development or commercial phase.

3.1 Earlier work on microfluidic standardization

For microfluidic modularity, no standards are available yet. There have however been several discussions on this topic in the past. From these discussions we collected the following:

In the context of this report, building blocks are considered to be components that have a standard interface together with other building blocks to form a complete system. Together with adapters and tubes of a microfluidic motherboard resp. manifold, they would form a complete system.

Standardisation of microfluidic connections has been extensively discussed in several articles and three important white papers: (see <https://microfluidics-association.org/downloads>)

- Design Guideline for Microfluidic Device and Component Interfaces (part 1), version 3.0
- Design Guideline for Microfluidic Device and Component Interfaces (part 2), version 3.0
- Design Guideline for Microfluidic Side Connect, version 1.0
- Guidelines for Packaging of Microfluidics: Electrical Interconnections

These guidelines are still valid and relevant. However, they aimed at the design of microfluidic chips. This was a good start, but failed to attract designers and manufacturers of microfluidic components like pumps, sensors, etc. We realised that there are two important boundary conditions to realise general acceptance of a microfluidic component standard interface:

1) The standard should be supported from the start by a substantial number of suppliers of microfluidic components and instruments. The successful implementation of standards like the SBS/AISI standards for the microtiterplate was driven by an industrial community.

2) Such standards (be it for fluid connectors, fluidic interfaces, modules) should provide solutions for a wide range of applications in order to make it attractive for suppliers of components.

3.2 Established standards from laboratory automation

Due to their importance and key influence on microfluidics, two standards from laboratory automation need to be mentioned, despite the fact that this document focuses at standardization options beyond laboratory automation:

1. **Microtiter plate:** The ANSI (American National Standards Institute) / SBS-Standard for microtiter plates
2. **Microscopy slide:** The ISO 8037: Width: 25 – 26 mm, length: 75 – 76 mm

These standards are widely used, also for some, although not all, microfluidic applications.

4 Modules, components and accessories – where standardization comes into play

The module concept in microfluidics makes sense if a wide variety of users have access to the devices and are willing to use these devices. Against this background, the industrial community needs to agree on a standard and implement this standard into their commercially available product offering.

It is also necessary to distinguish between the microfluidic modules, meaning the microfluidic chip itself, and the accessories like fluidic interfaces, liquid storage modules, sensors etc. to be used with them and elements being integrated like e.g. a sensor component.

4.1 Modular microfluidic components

Depending on the intended application, there are different requirements for modular microfluidic components. Preferably modular components are fabricated in such a way that they meet a substantial number of these requirements and can be used for a substantial part of the microfluidic market (the "hot-spot"). Also, the component should be designed in such a way that with moderate changes other market segments can be addressed too. Such expansion of the application space is to be covered by a roadmap. With this in mind the requirements can be divided in needs (essential for the "hot-spot") and wants (to expand the application space and to be addressed by a roadmap).

Although keeping in mind, the so-called “hot-spots” are not a consideration from all users, thus compared to existing solutions in the microfluidic and analytical world a “one-fits-all” solutions is unlikely to be defined.

4.2 Modular microfluidic components, corresponding instrument and accessories

In the context of this report, modular microfluidic components can be:

- Pumps
- Valves
- Fluid connectors
- Tubes
- Mixers
- Degassers
- Sensors
- Microfluidic chips
- Etc.

The functionalities these components supply, can in some case also be supplied by integration of building blocks heterogeneously.

5 Heterogenous integration

Heterogenous integration can cover topics like sensor integration, electrode integration, membranes, valves etc. Whilst some of the heterogenous integration topics are a manufacturing topic only, not requiring a special interface to the heterogenous component, two examples should be elaborated since they are interfacing and fabrication topics, namely electrode integration and sensor integration.

5.1 Heterogenous integration – electrode integration

Microfluidic devices often use various means for sample manipulation and detection. For example, electrophoresis, dielectrophoresis (DEP), acoustic waves, and surface acoustic waves (SAW) are commonly used for manipulating samples in flow, while integrated electrodes are used for electrochemical detection. Some of these methods require contact with liquid (such as electrochemical detection), and some could function with and without (e.g., DEP, SAW).

Metal electrodes are the most common elements integrated into microfluidic devices. These can be gold electrodes, Glass- ITO electrodes, and silicon-gold electrodes, where the electrodes are in direct contact with liquid.

Some of the constraints during the integration of heterogenous components are given below:

- Compatibility during fabrication processes. (For example, microfabrication of electrodes must fit into the process of making glass chips or plastic chips).
- The difference in height/surface roughness between the components could cause leakage. Usually, an electrode thickness of less than 500 nm is used, which does not cause leakage for low flow rate applications.
- Alignment issues: Electrodes are usually prepared on a separate surface from the channel and may cause alignment issues during the bonding process.
- The choice of conductivity and electrical parameters plays an important role.
- Joule heating can be induced, and the effect is significant when using a higher conductive solution, lower flow rate, lower frequency, high voltage etc. Corrosion of electrodes can also be significant under these conditions. This can damage the samples as well as destruction of the device.

- Contactless electrodes can be used to avoid above mentioned problems. However, there will be a need for higher AC voltages with high frequencies. The use of DC voltage may not give significantly good results.
- Surface treatment of the device is necessary to avoid sticking particles to the channel walls and the electrodes.

5.2 Heterogenous integration – Sensor integration

Silicon photonics is a hot topic in microfluidics: Semiconductor technologies are used to provide photonic based sensors. These silicon or glass-based sensors need to be integrated in microfluidic devices – glass or polymers – and their price scales massively with their size. Against this background, respective integration technologies are of interest, standardized interfaces of a microfluidic chip (size of integration area) and easy interfacing technology independent from the material also for small quantities is of interest.

6 Fluidic interfaces – most important feature in standardization

6.1 Interconnection of microfluidic modules and instruments

Some of the biggest technical hurdles in the assembly and performance of microfluidic devices are the microfluidic interfaces, especially interfacing with tube. There are dozens of different microfluidic connectors in use; to name a few: Luer, threaded, clamped, gaskets., having it pros and cons for the applications.

The biggest challenge is the incompatibility of connectors (including their dimensions and material type) between different components, secondly, connection systems are often difficult to use for non-engineers and incompatible with automatic assembly. Saying this, it should be stressed that for some commercial pathways existing standardized interfaces (Luer, threaded fitting from Liquid chromatography, gaskets) or specific for the microfluidic world developed ones (Mini Luer, olives, holes requiring a sealing interface, pipetting interfaces) might be a good solution. All other standards applied to these devices are defined by the world of laboratory automation, the ANSI/SLAS-standards defining a footprint (microtiter plate) and spacing between wells (9 mm, 4.5 mm, 2.25 mm) and providing all kind of commercial equipment for devices following those standards.

Although developed for other applications and not always optimal for microfluidic use. several of the interfaces used have been in routine use millions of times.

Allowing microfluidics, a better entry in the routine life science / analytical laboratory, designers and manufacturers of microfluidic components like pumps, sensors etc. need to be part of the overall interfacing concept as well.

Furthermore, there are four important boundary conditions to achieve general acceptance of a microfluidic component standard interface:

- 1) The standard should be supported from the start by a substantial number of suppliers of microfluidic components and instruments.
- 2) Such a connector standard should be applicable in a wide range of applications.
- 3) The use case needs to be described and the pros and cons of the solutions need to be evaluated.
- 4) Players outside the microfluidic community from laboratory automation, analytical science and end-users need to be involved.

6.2 Requirements

Before designing a standard microfluidic modular system, boundaries conditions or requirements should be carefully considered and defined. These requirements will be divided into “must-have- ones” and “nice-to-have-ones”. If these “nice-to-have-ones” are not feasible, inclusion in a roadmap should be considered, to be met later with second of third generation products, for instance multiple size standards for different classes of components (similar to SMT (Surface mount components) packages in electronics).

Over the years a number of surveys were conducted that led to the conclusion that most of the microfluidic users are working with aqueous fluids containing biological materials. As a consequence, they generally tend to work around room temperature, or slightly above that, and at low pressures. Those that include processes like PCR (polymerase chain reaction) or have the need to sterilize their equipment will of course need slightly higher temperatures. The outcome of other surveys and interviewing industry experts is that there is also a hotspot regarding flow rate.

Figure 2: major application area for microfluidics

Based on this, the first elements of the requirements could be formulated - the common working conditions for the system:

- Pressure up is to 2 bar .
- Operational temperature is between 4 °C and 50 °C.
- Flow rate is between 1 µL/min and 100 µL/min.
- Suitable for water-based fluids containing biomolecular matter.

On the wish list, it can be added the requirement that the developed system should give an opening for a second generation version that can withstand temperatures up to 120 °C and 7 bar. For an extension of the application area, one could think of suitability for other media, especially gases.

From the user’s perspective, there is a general demand that such a system should not have a negative impact on the functioning or the performance of the installations where the modules are part of. That leads to the following requirements for microfluidic parts:

- Low internal volume.
- No dead volume.
- Low flow resistivity.
- Limited risk of biofilm formation.

- Using only “biocompatible” materials as wetted materials.
- Leak tight.
- No materials that leach out material.

From an industrial point of view, the materials used should be affordable and the supply chain sufficiently covered.

Ease of use is an important aspect of the requirements, but one should also keep in mind that many users are doing microfluidic experiments using a flexible setup with the intention that after the experiments have led to positive results, the system is transformed into an industrial design. That means the system should facilitate a smooth transfer from the flexible first phase based on modules connected with tubes, to a second phase all microfluidic elements might be combined in the microfluidic device and hybrid elements like sensors might be mounted, for instance on a manifold. An important aspect of the design of fluidic connectors is the tubing. Although soft wall tubing is sometimes used (for instance when using a peristaltic pump or connecting differently sized fluid connectors or tubings), rigid tubing can be used as a starting point and defining a common outer diameter (OD) of 1/16” resp. 1.6 mm. Preferably the connector should be flexible for the tube's inner diameter (ID) and usable for soft wall tubing as well.

Other requirements which should be of benefit to the connection process:

- The connection system should be “fool proof” and easy to use but should also be usable in an industrial setting.
- The connection should have a pull resistance to prevent connection failure.
- Lowest “footprint” possible, no bulky connection parts.
- Design is freely available, but it is defined by a standard.
- Pathway for further integration.

Based on these requirements, the following market segments can be covered:

Table 1 Market segments that could benefit from a modular approach and their specific characteristics/needs

Market segments that could benefit from a modular approach	Specific characteristics/needs
Research	For research applications, flexibility and ease of connect are important aspects.
Analytical instruments	In analytical instrumentation reliability, low dead volume, ordered layout (separation electrical and fluidic lines), and a roadmap to further integration are important requirements.
Bioreactors ¹ ; “physical” reactors	The long-term use of those installations leads to specific requirements like pull resistance of the connectors and limited formation of biofilm.

Not all market segments are covered of course, important areas not covered are chemical reactors and handheld medical diagnostic devices.

Summary of the “**must-have**” requirements:

- Can withstand a pressure of 2 bar and a temperature of (4-50) °C .
- Suitable for flows of 1 µL/min to 100 µL/min.
- Water based fluids containing biomolecular matter.

¹ In the context of this discussing with bioreactors are seem as devices were biomaterials are in process for a prolonged period of time.

- Low internal volume.
- No dead volume.
- Low flow resistivity.
- Limited risk of biofilm formation.
- Using only “biocompatible” materials as wetted materials.
- Leak tight.
- No materials that leach out material.
- Materials used should be affordable and the supply chain sufficiently covered.
- Pathway to further integration.
- Pull resistance.

Wish list and roadmap:

- No special tooling required for making the connection.
- Can withstand temperatures up to 120 °C and pressures up to 7 bar.
- Suitable for gases and / or other media like oil and solvents.
- Sterilizable.
- Flexible for ID size and usable for soft wall tubing.
- Integration of optical components.

6.3 Interconnection of microfluidic modules and instruments – wish list

Based on the considerations outlined 4.2, the following table listing the “needs” and “wants” was created. It is important to stress, that “needs” and “wants” differ from application to application thus the table can serve for inspiration only. The only common ground is that a fluid connection should not leak, secondly some rather general requirements match nearly all applications.

Table 2: Requirements hotspot for microfluidics interfaces – the generic requirements are marked in green

Requirement	Needs	Wants (might be covered in the roadmap)
Reliability	Leak tight.	
Pressure	Maximum 2 bar	Maximum 10 bar
Temperature	(4-50) °C.	(4-120) °C.
Flow rate	1 µL/min to 100 µL/min.	(1-1000) µL/min.
Medium	Water based fluids containing biomolecular matter	Also gasses
Reliability	Leak tight	
Materials	“Biocompatible” materials as wetted materials, materials used should be affordable and the supply chain sufficiently covered	Fluor free
Availability	Design is freely available but fixed in a standard	
Connectivity	Compatible with microfluidic chips	
Other requirements	Low internal volume Low flow resistivity Limiting risk of biofilm formation	
Usage related requirements	Reusable / cleanable	Sterilizable
	Suitable for rigid tubing 1/16” / 1,6 mm OD tube	Flexible for ID size, soft wall tubing
	No need for special tooling to make the connections	“One click fastening”, tubing having pull resistance
	Design is freely available but fixed in a standard	
	Enabling seamless transfer from experimentation to mass-production; the same microfluidic parts that	Lowest “footprint” possible / not bulky

	are used in an experimental phase should be usable in an industrialized system	
	Compatibility with ISO 22916:2022 Microfluidic devices — Interoperability requirements for dimensions, connections, and initial device classification	

7 Issues to be covered by a standard for modular assembly

A standard for microfluidic modularity should cover only the essentials to achieve compatibility, i.e. the dimensions of the contact area:

- 1) Footprint of the interface between component and the system / manifold.
- 2) Area reserved for fixation (clamping or screwing).
- 3) Position of the portholes in the interface.
- 4) Sealing.

10. Metrological aspects

When such a modular system is designed and created, it is supposed to adhere to the requirements set previously. That means that measurement protocols should be defined and available and the devices should be well characterized in terms of:

- Dead volume.
- Internal volume.
- Flow resistivity.
- Leak tightness.

The related measurement procedures can be found in MFMET A2.2.2: Development of test protocols for microfluidic devices.

These measurements are crucial in validating the performance of microfluidic components and systems against the defined standard.

Metrology in microfluidics also extends to materials characterisation and compatibility assessment (biocompatibility, cytotoxicity, etc.). When using microfluidic chips for biological samples or living organisms, biocompatibility is a crucial material property to ensure that the materials and surfaces do not interact with or harm biological beings. Surface characterisation techniques, such as contact angle measurements and surface energy studies, enable the selection of suitable materials by offering significant information about the interaction between microfluidic surfaces and biological fluids. For long-term biological investigations within microfluidic devices, biofilm growth in the case of long-period biological assays (could pose a risk because it can cause blockage, changed fluid dynamics, and cross-contamination. Understanding the potential for biofilm adherence and growth requires a thorough understanding of the surface of the materials used that are in contact with the fluid.

11. Conclusions

In the first place, one should consider if adherence to already established common practices in the application space can be followed, for instance the ANSI (American National Standards Institute) / SBS-Standard for microtiter plates. Following this will facilitate the compatibility with the available microtiter plate workflows used by many laboratories.

When a microfluidic device is to be created modularly, standards are essential. Such standards are to be created by involving a large number of actors to ensure uptake in the market.

Furthermore, it should adhere to certain requirements that cover a wide range of applications (the hot-spot in microfluidics). See table 3.

Table 3: Requirements hot-spot for microfluidic modularity

Topic	Needs
Reliability	Leak tight
Pressure	Maximum 2 bar
Temperature	(4-50) °C
Flow rate	(1-100) µL/min
Medium	Aqueous fluids containing biomolecular matter
Materials	“Biocompatible” materials as wetted materials, materials used should be affordable and the supply chain sufficiently covered
Availability	Design is freely available but fixed in a standard
Connectivity	Compatible with microfluidic chips

Other requirements might depend on the application and might be covered by a roadmap.

Only a relatively small number of parameters needs to be covered by standard:

- Footprint of the interface between component and the system / manifold.
- Area reserved for fixation (clamping or screwing).
- Position of the portholes in the interface.
- Sealing.

Metrology protocols need to be developed (or existing protocols adapted) to ensure compatibility and proper functioning:

- Flow control related issues (Dead volume, internal volume, flow resistivity etc.).
- Material related issues (Cytotoxicity, biocompatibility etc.).
- Reliability related issues (Leak tightness, accelerated tests etc.).

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